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Research Article

**KNOWLEDGE, PERCEPTIONS, AND LIFESTYLE BEHAVIOR
MODIFICATIONS AND CHANGES RELATED TO HYPERTENSION IN
TAIF CITY, SAUDI ARABIA****Abdulaziz Husain Alfaifi¹, Danah Awwadh Al-Harthi², Ghaida Hesham Al-Omran²,
Raghad Awad Algorashi², Sara Ahmed Ali Assiri², Atheer Abdulraheem Alsufyani²,
Mona Mohamed Ali³, Hussain Saleh Baabbad⁴**¹ Department of Internal Medicine, King Abdulaziz Specialist Hospital, Taif, Saudi Arabia² College of Medicine, Taif University, Taif, Saudi Arabia³ Department of Forensic medicine and clinical toxicology, Taif University, Taif, Saudi Arabia⁴ Department of Internal Medicine, King Fahad Hospital, Taif, Saudi Arabia**Abstract**

Hypertension is a serious chronic medical disorder associated with considerable morbidity and mortality. Because, to date, there is no potential cure for the disease, prevention remains the mainstay for reduction of the disease burden. Identification and control of the risk factors for hypertension are the key for disease prevention. Therefore, the aim of this study was to explore the awareness, practices, and attitudes of Saudi population towards hypertension.

Methods: This was a cross-sectional study conducted via distributing a written questionnaire to inhabitants of Taif city in Saudi Arabia. Data from the gathered questionnaires were analyzed using IBM SPSS software.

Results: Of 322 participants, 71.4% were males, and 96.6% were educated. Salt overdose, obesity, hypercholesterolemia, and physical inactivity were the most common identified risk factors; they were appropriately identified by 92%, 90%, 83%, and 79% of the participants, respectively. Alcohol consumption (60%) and family history (59%) were the least identified factors. About 40% of the participants reported that they sometimes follow healthy diet. Replacing ordinary fat with low fat in diet was the most common healthy dietary practice reported to be always adopted (in 30% of participants). Elderly participants were less likely to reduce caffeine intake (42.9%), to replace ordinary fat with low fat (43%), and to adopt a no salt diet (35.7%). About 46% stated they sometimes increase their daily activity, and about 21% reported they always did not have time to exercise. Only 30% were keen on regular check-up of their weights. About 74% stated that they were trying to minimize work stress. Overthinking was more prevalent among 84% of the participants. About 56% of participants reported that they were avoiding cigarette smoking. Though 76.7% of participants knew that the medications were beneficial, 58.7% stated that they do not like taking a medicine.

Conclusion: The Saudi population in Taif city have a fair knowledge and awareness about the risk factors for hypertension. However, their attitudes and practices towards reducing many risk factors are negative, particularly weight reduction, physical activity, and dietary habits.

Keywords: Attitude, awareness, hypertension, knowledge, practices, Saudi Arabia.

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INTRODUCTION:

Hypertension is a serious chronic medical condition that is associated with considerable morbidity and mortality. It is estimated that 3.9 billion individual (or about 28.5-31.5% of the population) has hypertension worldwide, and the number is expected to increase to 1.56 billion in 2025[1–3]. Hypertension increases the risk for coronary heart disease, chronic kidney disease, ischemic cerebrovascular stroke, and cerebral haemorrhage, and it is estimated that more than one third of hypertensive patients develop serious complications [4,5]. In Saudi Arabia, a report from 2007 stated that hypertension affects about 27.9% of the population in the urban areas and about 22.4% of the population in rural areas, and the prevalence is increasing [6]. To date, there is no cure for hypertension and the currently available medications are to be taken regularly for life for control of the blood pressure [7]. Therefore, the mainstay for reduction of hypertension prevalence and the hypertension-related morbidity and mortality is to prevent the disease before its actual development.

Prevention of hypertension necessitates adequate awareness of the population about the risk factors of the disease and how to minimize or stop them [8]. Many factors have long been identified to increase the risk for hypertension such as old age, smoking, diabetes mellitus, dyslipidaemia, obesity, lack of physical activity, and over intake of salt in diet [9,10]. In Saudi Arabia, these risk factors are common. A national study conducted in 2013 in Saudi Arabia showed that the risk factors for hypertension were prevalent among Saudi population particularly obesity, diabetes, and hypercholesterolemia [11]. Moreover, more than half of the studied Saudi patients had their blood pressure poorly controlled [11]. The reason behind the high prevalence of hypertension risk factors in Saudi Arabia may be a lack of adequate knowledge and awareness about the disease and its causes and consequences. To the best of our knowledge, few studies have addressed this issue and focused on studying the Saudi population awareness about hypertension. Therefore, the aim of this study was to evaluate the knowledge, awareness, and practices adopted by Saudi population in Taif city towards hypertension.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This was a cross sectional study conducted in Taif city during the period from June to August 2018 A written questionnaire was distributed to 350 participants in Taif city (King Abdulaziz Specialist Hospital and King Faisal Hospitals). The

questionnaire included questions about the demographic data of participants (e.g. age, gender, marital status, and educational level). Participants were also asked whether they were smokers, they have stress, and they had family history chronic diseases (such as hypertension, diabetes, stroke, or coronary artery disease) or not. The second part of the questionnaire asked the participants about their knowledge of the risk factors of hypertension. They were asked whether they know or not that there is a relationship between hypertension and family history, old age, smoking, obesity, physical activity, stress, alcohol, high cholesterol level, certain medications, and salt overdosage. The third part of the questionnaire included questions about the practices adopted by participants for prevention of hypertension particularly dietary practices, weight reduction, and physical activity. The fourth and last partition of the questionnaire inquired about the awareness and attitude towards different risk factors.

All the gathered data were fed into a computer and analyzed using IBM Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22.0. All qualitative data were presented as numbers and percent, and the participants were categorized according to their age groups. P value was calculated to compare between the groups, and the level of significance was calculated at 5%.

RESULTS:

Of 355 questionnaires distributed, 322 participants responded. About three-fourths of the participants (71.4%) were males, and 78.6% were married. The vast majority (96.6%) were educated. The demographic data were not significantly different among the different age groups except for educational and marital status ($p < 0.001$). Almost half (48.6%) of the participants reported that they have a positive family history of hypertension. Smoking was common among the recruited participants, occurring in about 40% of them. The details of the demographic characteristics are depicted in table 1.

Table 1. Socio-demographic characteristics of the participants

Variables		Age Groups											P-Value	
		45-50		51-55		56-60		61-65		66-70		Total		
		N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N		%
Gender	Male	176	73.9%	27	64.3%	13	61.9%	4	57.1%	10	71.4%	230	71.4%	0.489
	Female	62	26.1%	15	35.7%	8	38.1%	3	42.9%	4	28.6%	92	28.6%	
Marital Status	Single	54	22.7%	2	4.8%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	1	7.1%	57	17.7%	< 0.001
	Married	180	75.6%	37	88.1%	20	95.2%	6	85.7%	10	71.4%	253	78.6%	
	Widowed	1	0.4%	2	4.8%	1	4.8%	1	14.3%	3	21.4%	8	2.5%	
	Divorced	3	1.3%	1	2.4%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	4	1.2%	
Education Status	Yes	237	99.6%	41	97.6%	19	90.5%	5	71.4%	9	64.3%	311	96.6%	< 0.001
	No	1	0.4%	1	2.4%	2	9.5%	2	28.6%	5	35.7%	11	3.4%	
Family History	Hypertension	92	45.3%	18	46.2%	12	66.7%	5	71.4%	8	72.7%	135	48.6%	0.292
	DM	106	52.2%	21	53.8%	6	33.3%	2	28.6%	2	18.2%	137	49.3%	
	Stroke	2	1.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	2	0.7%	
	CAD	3	1.5%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	1	9.1%	4	1.4%	
	Others	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	
Smoking Status	Yes	107	45.0%	14	33.3%	5	23.8%	2	28.6%	4	28.6%	132	41.0%	0.126
	No	131	55.0%	28	66.7%	16	76.2%	5	71.4%	10	71.4%	190	59.0%	
Cigarettes Per Day	5-1	17	16.8%	1	7.1%	2	33.3%	2	66.7%	1	20.0%	23	17.8%	0.126
	10-6	14	13.9%	2	14.3%	1	16.7%	1	33.3%	0	0.0%	18	14.0%	
	15-11	24	23.8%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	1	20.0%	25	19.4%	
	20-16	27	26.7%	5	35.7%	2	33.3%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	34	26.4%	
	More Than 20	19	18.8%	6	42.9%	1	16.7%	0	0.0%	3	60.0%	29	22.5%	

CAD: coronary heart disease, DM: diabetes mellitus

Upon studying the participants knowledge about the different risk factors for hypertension (table 2), it was noted the most commonly identified risk factors were salt overdose (91.9%) and obesity (89.8%). Next came the hypercholesterolemia (82.6%), physical inactivity (79.2%), smoking (77.6%), medications (70.8%), and stress (69.3%). Alcohol consumption and positive family history of

hypertension were the least identified factors known by 59.6% and 58.7% of the participants, respectively. Overall, the population awareness about risk factors was good as all risk factors were identified by at least half of the participants in Taif city. Also noted, the age did not have a significant impact on participants' knowledge about the different risk factors for hypertension ($p>0.05$).

Table 2. Assessment of the participants' knowledge regarding different risk factors

Variables		Age Groups												P-Value
		50-45		55-51		60-56		65-61		70-66		Total		
		N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	
Relation between HTN and family history	Yes	13 5	56.7 %	29	69.0 %	11	52.4 %	5	71.4%	9	64.3 %	18 9	58.7 %	0.158
	NO	33	13.9 %	2	4.8%	7	33.3 %	1	14.3%	2	14.3 %	45	14.0 %	
	I don't know	70	29.4 %	11	26.2 %	3	14.3 %	1	14.3%	3	21.4 %	88	27.3 %	
Relation between HTN and old age	Yes	17 9	75.2 %	35	83.3 %	13	61.9 %	5	71.4%	11	78.6 %	24 3	75.5 %	0.769
	NO	22	9.2%	1	2.4%	3	14.3 %	1	14.3%	1	7.1%	28	8.7%	
	I don't know	37	15.5 %	6	14.3 %	5	23.8 %	1	14.3%	2	14.3 %	51	15.8 %	
Relation between HTN and smoking	Yes	18 5	77.7 %	35	83.3 %	12	57.1 %	6	85.7%	12	85.7 %	25 0	77.6 %	0.065
	NO	8	3.4%	0	0.0%	2	9.5%	0	0.0%	2	14.3 %	12	3.7%	
	I don't know	45	18.9 %	7	16.7 %	7	33.3 %	1	14.3%	0	0.0%	60	18.6 %	
Relation between HTN and obesity	Yes	21 3	89.5 %	40	95.2 %	16	76.2 %	7	100.0 %	13	92.9 %	28 9	89.8 %	0.395
	No	2	0.8%	0	0.0%	1	4.8%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	3	0.9%	
	I don't know	23	9.7%	2	4.8%	4	19.0 %	0	0.0%	1	7.1%	30	9.3%	
Relation between HRN and physical inactivity	Yes	18 8	79.0 %	35	83.3 %	16	76.2 %	5	71.4%	11	78.6 %	25 5	79.2 %	0.972
	No	14	5.9%	1	2.4%	1	4.8%	1	14.3%	1	7.1%	18	5.6%	
	I don't know	36	15.1 %	6	14.3 %	4	19.0 %	1	14.3%	2	14.3 %	49	15.2 %	
Relation between HTN and stress	Yes	16 6	69.7 %	27	64.3 %	17	81.0 %	4	57.1%	9	64.3 %	22 3	69.3 %	0.565
	No	21	8.8%	5	11.9 %	0	0.0%	2	28.6%	1	7.1%	29	9.0%	
	I don't know	51	21.4 %	10	23.8 %	4	19.0 %	1	14.3%	4	28.6 %	70	21.7 %	

Relation between HTN and alcohol consumption	Yes	14 4	60.5 %	22	52.4 %	11	52.4 %	6	85.7%	9	64.3 %	19 2	59.6 %	0.859
	No	12	5.0%	3	7.1%	1	4.8%	0	0.0%	1	7.1%	17	5.3%	
	I don't know	82	34.5 %	17	40.5 %	9	42.9 %	1	14.3%	4	28.6 %	11 3	35.1 %	
Relation between HTN and high cholesterol	Yes	19 2	80.7 %	38	90.5 %	20	95.2 %	7	100.0 %	9	64.3 %	26 6	82.6 %	0.079
	No	2	0.8%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	1	7.1%	3	0.9%	
	I don't know	44	18.5 %	4	9.5%	1	4.8%	0	0.0%	4	28.6 %	53	16.5 %	
Relation between HTN and some medications	Yes	17 5	73.5 %	26	61.9 %	12	57.1 %	7	100.0 %	8	57.1 %	22 8	70.8 %	0.22
	No	6	2.5%	1	2.4%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	7	2.2%	
	I don't know	57	23.9 %	15	35.7 %	9	42.9 %	0	0.0%	6	42.9 %	87	27.0 %	
Relation between HTN and salt overuse	Yes	21 8	91.6 %	39	92.9 %	20	95.2 %	7	100.0 %	12	85.7 %	29 6	91.9 %	0.798
	No	3	1.3%	1	2.4%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	1	7.1%	5	1.6%	
	I don't know	17	7.1%	2	4.8%	1	4.8%	0	0.0%	1	7.1%	21	6.5%	

HTN: Hypertension

When studying the participants dietary practices, it was evident that less than one third of the population could stick regularly to different healthy dietary practices. Regular following of healthy dietary habits ranged from 8.1% (in reducing salt in diet) to 30% (in replacing ordinary with low fat diets). Most of the participants reported that they sometimes try to follow regular dietary habits. For instance, 47.8% of the participants stated that it is sometimes easy to follow healthy diets. About 44.4% and 39% reported that they sometimes eat fruits and vegetables, respectively. Unlike the general knowledge and awareness about risk factors of hypertension, the age of participants had a significant impact on the dietary practices. Elderly participants between 66 and 70 years of age were less likely to follow healthy dietary regimens. About 42% reported that they rarely replace ordinary fat with low fat, 42%

stated that they rarely reduce caffeine intake, and 35.7% reported that they rarely followed a “no salt” diet ($p < 0.05$) (table 3).

Assessing the physical activity and body weight practices (table 4), about 40% of the participants reported that, sometimes, there is no time for exercise. Increasing daily activity and doing daily sports was done sometimes by 45.7% and 34.5%, respectively. Regarding weight reduction, more than one third of the participants (36%) stated that they always needed tips to reduce their weight, and 18.3% reported that they could not reduce their weight at all. Moreover, about 15% of the participants stated that they had never a regular check of their body weight. The practices of body weight reduction and physical activity were not statistically significant among different age groups ($p > 0.05$) (table 4).

Table 3. Assessment of Participants' Different Diet Practices

Variables		Age Groups												P-Value
		50-45		55-51		60-56		65-61		70-66		Total		
		N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	
Healthy diet to lower blood pressure	always	32	13.4 %	7	16.7 %	2	9.5%	2	28.6 %	3	21.4 %	46	14.3 %	0.638
	sometimes	88	37.0 %	21	50.0 %	12	57.1 %	3	42.9 %	6	42.9 %	130	40.4 %	
	rare	54	22.7 %	8	19.0 %	3	14.3 %	1	14.3 %	3	21.4 %	69	21.4 %	
	never	64	26.9 %	6	14.3 %	4	19.0 %	1	14.3 %	2	14.3 %	77	23.9 %	
Easy to adjust diet	always	31	13.0 %	10	23.8 %	4	19.0 %	3	42.9 %	3	21.4 %	51	15.8 %	0.169
	sometimes	111	46.6 %	24	57.1 %	12	57.1 %	1	14.3 %	6	42.9 %	154	47.8 %	
	rare	52	21.8 %	5	11.9 %	3	14.3 %	2	28.6 %	4	28.6 %	66	20.5 %	
	never	44	18.5 %	3	7.1%	2	9.5%	1	14.3 %	1	7.1%	51	15.8 %	
Healthy diet	always	21	8.8%	7	16.7 %	1	4.8%	1	14.3 %	3	21.4 %	33	10.2 %	0.305
	sometimes	90	37.8 %	19	45.2 %	12	57.1 %	4	57.1 %	3	21.4 %	128	39.8 %	
	rare	65	27.3 %	7	16.7 %	2	9.5%	1	14.3 %	5	35.7 %	80	24.8 %	

	never	62	26.1 %	9	21.4 %	6	28.6 %	1	14.3 %	3	21.4 %	81	25.2 %	
Eating meals with saturated fat	always	48	20.2 %	8	19.0 %	2	9.5%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	58	18.0 %	0.051
	sometimes	134	56.3 %	20	47.6 %	16	76.2 %	3	42.9 %	7	50.0 %	180	55.9 %	
	rare	46	19.3 %	10	23.8 %	3	14.3 %	3	42.9 %	4	28.6 %	66	20.5 %	
	never	10	4.2%	4	9.5%	0	0.0%	1	14.3 %	3	21.4 %	18	5.6%	
Eating fruits and vegetables	always	45	18.9 %	16	38.1 %	6	28.6 %	6	85.7 %	6	42.9 %	79	24.5 %	0.001*
	sometimes	109	45.8 %	18	42.9 %	12	57.1 %	0	0.0%	4	28.6 %	143	44.4 %	
	rare	65	27.3 %	7	16.7 %	3	14.3 %	1	14.3 %	2	14.3 %	78	24.2 %	
	never	19	8.0%	1	2.4%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	2	14.3 %	22	6.8%	
Eating food without salt	always	14	5.9%	6	14.3 %	1	4.8%	3	42.9 %	2	14.3 %	26	8.1%	0.017*
	sometimes	73	30.7 %	18	42.9 %	9	42.9 %	3	42.9 %	2	14.3 %	105	32.6 %	
	rare	71	29.8 %	9	21.4 %	5	23.8 %	0	0.0%	5	35.7 %	90	28.0 %	
	never	80	33.6 %	9	21.4 %	6	28.6 %	1	14.3 %	5	35.7 %	101	31.4 %	
High fiber diet	always	35	14.7 %	10	23.8 %	2	9.5%	2	28.6 %	3	21.4 %	52	16.1 %	0.815
	sometimes	96	40.3 %	15	35.7 %	10	47.6 %	3	42.9 %	4	28.6 %	128	39.8 %	
	rare	62	26.1 %	10	23.8 %	7	33.3 %	2	28.6 %	5	35.7 %	86	26.7 %	
	never	45	18.9 %	7	16.7 %	2	9.5%	0	0.0%	2	14.3 %	56	17.4 %	
Taking omega 3	always	22	9.2%	6	14.3 %	3	14.3 %	3	42.9 %	0	0.0%	34	10.6 %	0.082
	sometimes	48	20.2 %	13	31.0 %	2	9.5%	1	14.3 %	3	21.4 %	67	20.8 %	
	rare	77	32.4 %	14	33.3 %	7	33.3 %	3	42.9 %	5	35.7 %	106	32.9 %	

	never	91	38.2 %	9	21.4 %	9	42.9 %	0	0.0%	6	42.9 %	115	35.7 %	
Replacing ordinary milk with low fat one	always	66	27.7 %	15	35.7 %	9	42.9 %	5	71.4 %	2	14.3 %	97	30.1 %	0.048*
	sometimes	76	31.9 %	10	23.8 %	8	38.1 %	0	0.0%	1	7.1%	95	29.5 %	
	rare	39	16.4 %	7	16.7 %	1	4.8%	1	14.3 %	5	35.7 %	53	16.5 %	
	never	57	23.9 %	10	23.8 %	3	14.3 %	1	14.3 %	6	42.9 %	77	23.9 %	
Reducing caffeine intake	always	20	8.4%	6	14.3 %	5	23.8 %	4	57.1 %	1	7.1%	36	11.2 %	0.003*
	sometimes	89	37.4 %	16	38.1 %	8	38.1 %	2	28.6 %	2	14.3 %	117	36.3 %	
	rare	47	19.7 %	5	11.9 %	4	19.0 %	1	14.3 %	6	42.9 %	63	19.6 %	
	never	82	34.5 %	15	35.7 %	4	19.0 %	0	0.0%	5	35.7 %	106	32.9 %	

Table 4. Assessment of Participants' Physical Activity/Body Weight Practices and Attitudes

Variables		Age Groups												P-Value
		50-45		55-51		60-56		65-61		70-66		Total		
		N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	
Daily sports	Always	34	14.3 %	9	21.4 %	1	4.8 %	1	14.3 %	1	7.1 %	46	14.3 %	0.294
	Sometimes	81	34.0 %	16	38.1 %	8	38.1 %	2	28.6 %	4	28.6 %	111	34.5 %	
	Rare	89	37.4 %	12	28.6 %	11	52.4 %	4	57.1 %	4	28.6 %	120	37.3 %	
	Never	34	14.3 %	5	11.9 %	1	4.8 %	0	0.0 %	5	35.7 %	45	14.0 %	
Increasing daily Activity	Always	44	18.5 %	13	31.0 %	4	19.0 %	3	42.9 %	2	14.3 %	66	20.5 %	0.478
	Sometimes	112	47.1 %	18	42.9 %	10	47.6 %	3	42.9 %	4	28.6 %	147	45.7 %	
	Rare	54	22.7 %	8	19.0 %	4	19.0 %	1	14.3 %	4	28.6 %	71	22.0 %	
	Never	28	11.8 %	3	7.1 %	3	14.3 %	0	0.0 %	4	28.6 %	38	11.8 %	

No time for Exercise	Always	54	22.7 %	9	21.4 %	4	19.0 %	1	14.3 %	1	7.1 %	69	21.4 %	0.226
	Sometimes	98	41.2 %	11	26.2 %	11	52.4 %	4	57.1 %	5	35.7 %	129	40.1 %	
	Rare	52	21.8 %	15	35.7 %	3	14.3 %	0	0.0 %	3	21.4 %	73	22.7 %	
	Never	34	14.3 %	7	16.7 %	3	14.3 %	2	28.6 %	5	35.7 %	51	15.8 %	
Checking weight Regularly	Always	69	29.0 %	14	33.3 %	7	33.3 %	2	28.6 %	2	14.3 %	94	29.2 %	0.298
	Sometimes	65	27.3 %	14	33.3 %	8	38.1 %	2	28.6 %	2	14.3 %	91	28.3 %	
	Rare	69	29.0 %	9	21.4 %	2	9.5 %	2	28.6 %	4	28.6 %	86	26.7 %	
	Never	35	14.7 %	5	11.9 %	4	19.0 %	1	14.3 %	6	42.9 %	51	15.8 %	
Cannot reduce Weight	Always	40	16.8 %	10	23.8 %	5	23.8 %	2	28.6 %	2	14.3 %	59	18.3 %	0.598
	Sometimes	79	33.2 %	17	40.5 %	6	28.6 %	2	28.6 %	4	28.6 %	108	33.5 %	
	Rare	59	24.8 %	7	16.7 %	2	9.5 %	0	0.0 %	4	28.6 %	72	22.4 %	
	Never	60	25.2 %	8	19.0 %	8	38.1 %	3	42.9 %	4	28.6 %	83	25.8 %	
Need a Tip to Reduce Weight	Always	95	39.9 %	12	28.6 %	4	19.0 %	3	42.9 %	2	14.3 %	116	36.0 %	0.219
	Sometimes	61	25.6 %	14	33.3 %	10	47.6 %	1	14.3 %	3	21.4 %	89	27.6 %	
	Rare	25	10.5 %	5	11.9 %	1	4.8 %	1	14.3 %	4	28.6 %	36	11.2 %	
	Never	57	23.9 %	11	26.2 %	6	28.6 %	2	28.6 %	5	35.7 %	81	25.2 %	

The participants awareness about having risk factors for hypertension and their attitudes towards these risk factors were also studied. About three-fourths (73.3%) of the participants were aware of having stress, and the awareness was significantly different among age groups. Participants between 51 and 55 years of age were the least group to report having stress (52.4%) ($p=0.024$). Of interest, more than 74%

stated that they were trying to minimize work stress. Overthinking was more prevalent than having stress, with almost 84% of the participants reporting it. Also, 56% of participants reported that they were avoiding cigarette smoking. Though 76.7% of participants knew that the medications were beneficial, 58.7% stated that they do not like taking a medicine.

Table 5. Assessment of participants' awareness and attitudes towards different risk factors

Variables		Age Groups												P-Value
		50-45		55-51		60-56		65-61		70-66		Total		
		N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	
Having Stress	Yes	18 2	76.5 %	22	52.4 %	17	81.0 %	5	71.4 %	10	71.4 %	23 6	73.3 %	0.024*
	No	56	23.5 %	20	47.6 %	4	19.0 %	2	28.6 %	4	28.6 %	86	26.7 %	
Trying to Minimize Work Stress	Yes	18 4	77.3 %	31	73.8 %	13	61.9 %	5	71.4 %	7	50.0 %	24 0	74.5 %	0.125
	No	54	22.7 %	11	26.2 %	8	38.1 %	2	28.6 %	7	50.0 %	82	25.5 %	
Overthinking	Yes	20 5	86.1 %	33	78.6 %	16	76.2 %	5	71.4 %	10	71.4 %	26 9	83.5 %	0.289
	No	33	13.9 %	9	21.4 %	5	23.8 %	2	28.6 %	4	28.6 %	53	16.5 %	
Avoiding Cigarette Smoking	Yes	12 2	51.3 %	29	69.0 %	15	71.4 %	4	57.1 %	9	64.3 %	17 9	55.6 %	0.114
	No	11 6	48.7 %	13	31.0 %	6	28.6 %	3	42.9 %	5	35.7 %	14 3	44.4 %	
Failure to Avoid Smoking and/or Alcohol	Yes	82	34.5 %	12	28.6 %	2	9.5% %	1	14.3 %	5	35.7 %	10 2	31.7 %	0.142
	No	15 6	65.5 %	30	71.4 %	19	90.5 %	6	85.7 %	9	64.3 %	22 0	68.3 %	
Don't Like Medications	Yes	16 0	67.2 %	18	42.9 %	4	19.0 %	3	42.9 %	4	28.6 %	18 9	58.7 %	< 0.001
	No	78	32.8 %	24	57.1 %	17	81.0 %	4	57.1 %	10	71.4 %	13 3	41.3 %	
Medications will Help Feeling Better	Yes	17 5	73.5 %	37	88.1 %	20	95.2 %	5	71.4 %	10	71.4 %	24 7	76.7 %	0.067
	No	63	26.5 %	5	11.9 %	1	4.8% %	2	28.6 %	4	28.6 %	75	23.3 %	

DISCUSSION:

Hypertension is a serious public health problem that affects more than one fourth of the Saudi population (22.4%-27.9%) [6]. In a community-based study conducted on 17,230 Saudi individuals recruited between 1995 to 2000, the researchers stated that hypertension in Saudi Arabia was significantly associated with high risk (8.2%) of coronary artery disease in comparison with normal healthy

counterparts (4.5%) ($P < 0.001$) (6). Prevention of hypertension is fundamental to reduce the risk of such grave complications [12,13]. The most successful strategy to prevent hypertension is to focus on controlling the risk factors [10,14]. Controlling these factors necessitate adequate education of the community about these risk factors and the ways and importance of their control. In Saudi Arabia, many literature studies have reported that some risk factors

for hypertension are notably prevalent. For instance, Al-Nozha et al., in 2007, reported that obesity was very common among hypertensive Saudi patients, and that it had a significant linear positive correlation with hypertension prevalence [6]. Charbel El Bcheraoui et al., in a national study conducted in Saudi Arabia in 2013, noted that smoking, hypercholesterolemia, obesity, and physical inactivity were prevalent in 92%, 61%, 52%, 40%, of the studied hypertensive patients, respectively [11]. Moreover, up to 32% reported that they were not eating any fruits or vegetables on daily basis. Therefore, public awareness of the importance of simple measures, such as weight reduction, following a healthy diet regimen, exercise, avoiding smoking, and minimizing the psychological stress, may have a major impact on reducing the prevalence as well as the complications of hypertension.

The aim of this study was to explore the public awareness about the risk factors of hypertension and their practices and attitudes towards these risk factors. Of interest, the results of our study showed that the Saudi population had good awareness about the risk factors for hypertension. All the ten risk factors included (i.e. positive family history, old age, smoking, physical inactivity, stress, alcohol consumption, high cholesterol drugs, and salt overdose) were identified by at least half of the study participants. In agreement with our results, data from a similar study conducted in Jeddah in 2017 showed that the percent of correct awareness about risk factors of hypertension among the public ranged from 50 to 92% [15]. The awareness level among hypertensive Saudi patients was also reported to be as high as 72% in another study [16]. In our study, salt overdose and obesity were the most common well-identified risk factors. Less than two-thirds of the participants knew that alcohol consumption and positive family history are risk factors for hypertension. Thus, despite the fair knowledge and awareness encountered among Saudi population, more focused educational programs are still recommended to shed the light on important, yet less commonly identified, risk factors for hypertension.

Though the studied participants seemed to have good knowledge about hypertension risk factors, their attitudes and practices were far from appropriateness. For instance, about 90% of the participants knew that obesity is a risk factor for hypertension. However, only 29% were checking their weights regularly, more than 25% stated they could never reduce their weight, and more than 36% reported that they always needed tips for weight reduction. Similarly, whilst 92% of the participants stated that salt overdose is

risky, only 8% adopted a 'no salt' diet. Also, 21% stated that they had no time for exercise, 22% had never tried to increase their daily activity, and only 14% were following regular daily sports whereas more than three-fourths (79.2%) of them knew the risk of physical inactivity in the development of hypertension. In contrary to the results of our study, Lama Bakhshlet al., in their study of hypertensive Saudi patients, noted that 79%, 57%, and 55.7% of the patients had low salt diet, did regular exercise, and had weight loss, respectively [16]. Taking both results together, it seems that the patients are keener on controlling their risk factors than the public, and this is another important point to be considered during the development of educational programs for the public. Public health education programs should educate the individuals about the necessity and importance of early and primary prevention of hypertension via controlling the risk factors even before the disease occurrence [8,9,17–19]. On the other hands, the participants in our study had fairly good attitudes towards avoiding smoking and minimizing work stress.

Compliance to medications is another important strategy to prevent serious complications of hypertension [20]. Reports from previous literature studies in Saudi Arabia showed that the vast majority of hypertensive patients are compliant to medications (83.7%) [16,21]. However, in our study, though about 77% stated that they knew the benefit of hypertensive medications, only 41% reported that they might like to take them. The importance of medication is also to be emphasized through the health education programs to reduce the risk of hypertension-associated complications.

CONCLUSION:

Despite the good knowledge and awareness of the Saudi population about the risk factors for hypertension, the attitudes and practices towards reducing or avoiding these risk factors were negative. The vast majority of the studied participants did not have adequate physical activity, weight reduction, or healthy dietary habits. The attitudes, however, were positive towards avoiding smoking and trying to minimize the psychological or work stress. Educational programs in Saudi Arabia should, thus, focus on training the public about easily adoptable methods to enhance the control of different risk factors of hypertension in the Saudi community.

LIST OF SYMBOLS AND ABBREVIATIONS

CAD: Coronary artery disease

DM: Diabetes Mellitus

HTN: Hypertension

SPSS: Statistical Package for the Social Sciences

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